

Evaluating lithium recovery using electrochemical membrane separation: cost analysis and design strategies

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Abstract

The increasing demand for Li-based chemicals necessitates advancements in sustainable recovery technologies. Ion-exchange membranes, such as Li superionic conductors, offer promising electrochemical solutions. However, the relationship between electrochemical fundamentals and techno-economic feasibility remains underexplored. This analysis presents a techno-economic evaluation of an integrated Li_2CO_3 production process, covering brine intake and pretreatment, direct electrochemical Li recovery, brine disposal, and LiCl conversion to battery-grade Li_2CO_3 . We develop an optimization method that accounts for variations in brine composition (Li: 0.17-710 ppm) and Li-selective membrane prices (\$500-\$40,000/m²) to establish stack design and operational guidelines to minimize energy and material consumption in producing 1 ton of Li_2CO_3 per day. We examine Li/Ca and Li/Mg selectivity, stack pressure drop limits, and operation at reduced recovery ratios. While a 20-bar pressure threshold is identified as optimal for cost savings, we highlight an alternative strategy- combining lower recovery ratios with adaptive

electrochemical design- to further minimize costs without requiring higher pressure tolerance. While Li recovery from seawater remains costly, our findings indicate that for other brine sources, assuming a Li transference number of 1, production costs range from \$2,600 to \$28,000 per ton of Li_2CO_3 , with energy consumption varying from 5,099 to 71,099 kWh, depending on Li concentration and membrane price. However, energy demand can increase by 170% to over 900% at lower binary selectivities of ~ 22 to ~ 5 , primarily due to higher current density and voltage requirements. Our work provides guidelines on an efficient direct Li recovery from brines, paving the way to a more sustainable Li sourcing.

Introduction

The transition to low-carbon energy technologies has driven a growing demand for energy transition metals, including Li, Co, and Ni.^{1,2} Among these, Li is particularly crucial for renewable energy systems, especially in Li-ion batteries,³⁻⁵ and has experienced a notable increase in demand in recent years.⁶ In 2022, global Li consumption was estimated at 134 kt, a 41% increase from 95 kt in 2021.⁷ The average price of lithium carbonate equivalent (LCE) is around \$10,000 per ton, with spikes reaching up to \$68,000 per ton in 2022.⁸ This growth trajectory and price volatility highlight the need for sustainable mineral extraction, recovery, and conversion practices. Electrochemical recovery techniques present a promising solution, offering advantages such as lower water consumption compared to evaporation ponds, a controllable extraction rate, integration with renewable energy sources, and applicability to water sources of varying composition. Additionally, recovering minerals from water and brine sources can help mitigate supply risks for elements with limited geological deposits.⁹

Among electrochemical recovery methods, the use of Li-selective membranes (LiSMs) based on Li superionic conductors (Li-SICs) emerges as a promising approach. Li-SICs constitute a unique

class of solid-state electrolytes with the potential for high Li selectivity (Figure 1A), which has been demonstrated in Li recovery from seawater.¹⁰⁻¹³ For instance, Li et al. reported a Li/Mg selectivity of approximately 400,000 and a Li/Ca selectivity of around 320,000 for Li recovery from seawater using the perovskite-type $\text{Li}_{0.33}\text{La}_{0.56}\text{TiO}_3$ SIC in an electro dialysis (ED) setup.¹⁴ Jing Xu et al. recycled high-purity Li from spent Li-ion batteries using the garnet-type $\text{Li}_{6.5}\text{La}_3\text{Zr}_{0.5}\text{Ta}_{1.5}\text{O}_{12}$ (LLZTO) electrolyte.¹⁵ More recently, Han et al. deposited NASICON-type $\text{Li}_{1.3}\text{Al}_{0.3}\text{Ti}_{1.7}(\text{PO}_4)_3$ (LATP) on high-strength, porous alumina and demonstrated Li recovery from a solution with a Mg/Li ratio of 40 using a scalable membrane-based ED process.¹⁶ Besides Li-SICs, high Li-selective performance has also been reported with ion-functionalized metal-organic frameworks (MOFs), achieving a Li/Mg selectivity of approximately 1800 and a Li/Ca selectivity of around 150.^{17, 18}

For widely recognized Li-SICs such as the sulfide-type $\text{Li}_{10}\text{GeP}_2\text{S}_{12}$ (LGPS), molecular dynamics simulations have revealed multi-ion hopping as the predominant mechanism for Li transport along the diffusion pathway.¹⁹⁻²¹ In contrast to isolated, individual ion hopping, multi-ion hopping associated with Li migration exhibits a lower activation energy and, consequently, results in higher diffusivity as compared to other ions (Figure 1B).^{19, 22} The unique combination of high diffusivity (D_{Li}) and elevated concentration (n_{cLi}) within Li-SICs presents an enticing prospect for achieving high migration selectivity for Li,²³ as expressed in eq. 1:

$$\frac{j_{\text{Li}}}{j_{j \neq \text{Li}}} \sim \frac{z_{\text{Li}}^2}{z_j^2} \times \frac{D_{\text{Li}} \cdot n_{\text{cLi}}}{D_j \cdot n_{\text{cj}}} \sim \frac{z_{\text{Li}}^2 \cdot n_{\text{cLi}} \times \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta G_{\text{mig, Li}}}{RT}\right)}{z_j^2 \cdot n_{\text{cj}} \times \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta G_{\text{mig, j}}}{RT}\right)} \quad (\text{eq. 1})$$

where j represents the ion flux through the membrane, and z denotes the ionic valence. The potential for high migration selectivity with Li-SICs opens the door to Li recovery from brines with relatively low Li concentration.

The high selectivity offered by Li-SICs makes electrochemical Li recovery increasingly promising. However, there is a significant knowledge gap regarding the relationship between the fundamental aspects of this process and its overall techno-economics.²⁴ This work aims to bridge that gap by providing a techno-economic analysis (TEA) of a conceptual electrochemical Li recovery unit, in which a LiSM serves as the cation exchange membrane (CEM) and is paired with a typical anion exchange membrane (AEM) in an ED setup to recover Li from a dilute stream. The TEA in this study is based on a nonlinear optimization model that utilizes input parameters entirely derived from the literature, including membrane properties, brine compositions and physical properties, hydrodynamic conditions, electrochemical stack characteristics, and cost assumptions. The goal is to identify design configurations that minimize the cost of Li_2CO_3 production by adapting the electrochemical process layout to both the feedwater characteristics and the price of LiSMs. Embedding this adaptive optimization within the TEA, allows for flexible, scenario-based insights into the economic feasibility of electrochemical Li recovery, supporting informed decision-making for both process development and commercialization.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the underlying mechanisms driving the unique performance of Li-SICs in electrochemical Li recovery.

(A) Schematic illustrating the recovery of the target Li ion through electromigration from a feed stream. Notably, Li ion also serves as the primary mobile cation within the Li-SIC. Blue particles represent Li ions, while other colors denote other cations present in the feed.

(B) The high mobile Li ion concentration with a particular sublattice configuration in Li-SIC provides a reduced migration barrier and increased diffusivity for the Li ion in comparison to other ions present in the brine feed (the graph is a schematic representation). The migration path and associated energy profiles are mainly determined by the crystal structure and composition.^{22, 25}

Results and discussion

Process overview and key assumptions. Figure 2 illustrates the three main stages proposed in this study to produce Li_2CO_3 via an electrochemical recovery process employing a LiSM. The overall process is modeled as a continuous system and consists of the following key stages: (1) intake and pretreatment (pre-electrochemical processing), (2) electrochemical Li recovery, and (3) conversion to Li_2CO_3 (post-electrochemical processing). The first stage involves using intake pumps to transport the brine source to membrane filtration, which removes suspended particles and ensures an efficient electrochemical process.²⁶⁻²⁸ In the second stage, a LiSM serving as the CEM is paired with a typical AEM to form a cell pair. In this study, Fumasep membranes were modeled as the AEM, while data for LiSMs were sourced from commercial Li-SICs and LiSMs reported in the literature. The area resistance values used in the model were calculated as mid-average values derived from the available datasets (for more information, see Methods). The cell pair functions as a repeating unit within the electrochemical stack, with the aim of producing a Li-

rich stream with an elevated Li concentration in the form of LiCl during a single-pass recovery stage. The third stage involves the conversion of LiCl in the Li-rich stream to Li_2CO_3 using Na_2CO_3 as a precipitating agent.^{29, 30} In this study, the feed stream refers to the Li-dilute brine stream entering the electrochemical stack. The recovery stream denotes the Li-concentrated stream, where Li concentration increases progressively along the flow path during the electrochemical recovery process. The Li-rich stream refers to the recovery stream at its outlet, where Li has reached the required specifications for downstream processing.

Figure 2. Schematic representation of the proposed process for Li_2CO_3 production through an electrochemical Li recovery stage.

The process consists of three stages designed to convert Li from a brine source into Li_2CO_3 using a Li-selective exchange membrane. It operates in a continuous mode, where pre-treated brine undergoes de-lithiation in a single-pass electrochemical stack, achieving the targeted Li recovery. The recovered Li is subsequently processed through a precipitation stage operated at 80°C to form Li_2CO_3 . The Li-depleted stream is disposed into the brine source.

Table 1. Process cost components considered in this study for evaluating the total process cost of Li_2CO_3 production.

Cost components considered in this study for Li_2CO_3 production		
<p>Pre-electrochemical process stage</p> <p>CAPEX:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Capital expenditure for pre-treatment membrane filtration *Offshore intake pipe construction <p>OPEX:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Energy costs for pre-treatment filtration *Energy costs for intake pump 	<p>Electrochemical Li recovery stage</p> <p>CAPEX:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Li selective membrane *Anion exchange membrane *Stack capital expenditure *Auxiliary equipment <p>OPEX:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Labor and maintenance *Energy cost related to stack pressure drop *Energy cost from cell resistance 	<p>Post-electrochemical process stage</p> <p>CAPEX:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Construction costs for the brine discharge infrastructure <p>OPEX:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Chemical expenses for conversion from LiCl to Li_2CO_3 *Energy costs for the LiCl to Li_2CO_3 conversion stage *Energy costs associated with the brine discharge stage

In this study, production cost is derived from the power and material requirements at each stage of the extraction process. Throughout the analysis, a production capacity of 1 ton (metric ton) of Li_2CO_3 per day is assumed as the reference scale for TEA. Chloride is assumed to be the main counter-ion in the brine for the anion exchange process (see Methods and Source Data for Figure 4). Given the significant impact of Mg and Ca impurities on Li_2CO_3 precipitation,³¹⁻³³ minimum Li/Mg and Li/Ca ratios of 61 are considered as a criterion for a Li-rich stream to ensure high-purity Li_2CO_3 extraction.³⁴⁻³⁶ Identical pressure drops were applied to both the feed and recovery streams. Although the potential impact of operating at higher pressure drops (above 5 bar) on stack investment is acknowledged, these additional costs were not considered in this study due to the lack of established correlations between stack pressure drop limits and the associated capital expenditures for stack manufacturing. In this study, we adopt the pre-treatment procedures commonly used in membrane-based desalination processes, as detailed in references (see also Note S1).³⁷⁻⁴⁰ This approach is analogous to an ED desalination plant, as both ED desalination and electrochemical membrane-based Li recovery involve the dilute and concentrate streams flow through cell pairs containing AEMs and CEMs. The well-established pre-treatment techniques ensure the removal of suspended matter that can cause membrane fouling and improve the efficiency of ion exchange membranes. The process cost components used to evaluate Li_2CO_3 production are summarized in Table 1. Key model assumptions and input parameters are listed in Table 2. Notably, the membrane replacement factor was based on reported values for conventional polymeric membranes, as corresponding data for Li-SICs remain limited. For the Li-depleted stream, a slight decrease in total dissolved salinity relative to the feed is expected. Accordingly, surface water disposal²⁷ was assumed for returning this stream to the original brine source. For wholesale electricity, a value of 0.077 USD/kWh was used, representing the 2023 average based

on market data.⁴¹ The key assumptions listed in Table 2 represent current typical values based on the literature and market data. However, parameters such as current utilization and interest rate are subject to change as technology improves, and market conditions evolve. Future variations in these inputs could affect the economic and technical performance of Li_2CO_3 production.

The optimization process aimed to minimize the overall cost of Li_2CO_3 production by identifying the optimal internal design of the electrochemical stack. The three key design (free) variables were channel thickness (h), total flow width-to-length (W/L) ratio, and spacer mesh (filament) size (L_f). These parameters collectively control the stack's hydrodynamic conditions, pressure drop, and mass transfer performance, and thus determine the limiting current density and required membrane area. The model assumes operation at limiting current density (or a fixed fraction thereof), which is computed as a function of the optimized parameters and not independently varied. The optimization was conducted separately for each combination of brine composition and LiSM price. Full details of the optimization framework, constraints, and supporting equations are provided in the Methods and Notes S1-S10 in the supplementary information.

In the first part of this work, we introduce the concept of electrochemical process optimization and associated design parameters. We then provide a general assessment of the electrochemical Li recovery process from various brines, using the production of 1 ton of LCE per day as the base case. The objectives of this section are twofold: (i) to explore the implications of brine composition and the price of LiSM on electrochemical process design, and (ii) to evaluate various cost and energy components of the total process for an optimized stack design. Here, the term “total process” refers to all three stages involved in Li_2CO_3 production, as shown in Figure 2. For these analyses, we assumed a Li transference number of 1, representing an ideal scenario with 100% selectivity, which is supported by the high selectivity values reported for Li-SICs in the literature.

For instance, Hishino et al.¹² and Yang et al.¹⁰ each reported a Li transference number of 1 for $\text{Li}_2\text{O}-\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3-\text{SiO}_2-\text{P}_2\text{O}_5-\text{TiO}_2-\text{GeO}_2$ and $\text{Li}_{1.3}-\text{Al}_{0.3}-\text{Ti}_{1.7}-(\text{PO}_4)_3$ Li-SICs, respectively. Li et al.¹⁴ reported Li/Mg and Li/Ca selectivities of 400,000 and 320,000, respectively, for perovskite-type $\text{La}_{0.57}-\text{Li}_{0.29}-\text{TiO}_3$ Li-SIC, and Wang et al.⁴² reported a Li/Mg selectivity of $\sim 200,000$ for LISICON-type $\text{Li}_{1.5}-\text{Al}_{0.5}-\text{Ge}_{1.5}-\text{P}_3\text{O}_{12}$.

Following the general assessment of the process, the study addresses the impact of the stack pressure drop limit- the maximum pressure drops the electrochemical stack can handle- on electrochemical process cost. The subsequent section evaluates the influence of recovery ratio (deviations from the base case of 85%) and current density (reduced values compared to the limiting current) as process parameters affecting both cost and pressure drop. In the final section, Mg and Ca leakages (deviations from a Li transference number of 1) will be examined, and implications on required membrane area and energy consumption will be addressed for representative brines. Unless otherwise stated, optimization in this study focuses on the electrochemical process stage. The costs of other stages are included as functions of Li concentration in the brine feed, source location, and the target composition of the Li-rich stream (Methods and Notes S1 and S4).

Table 2 | Key assumptions and input parameters for the analysis of Li₂CO₃ production

Description	Values	References
Current utilization	0.9	Lee et al.,2002 ⁴³ ; Doornbusch et al., 2020 ⁴⁴
Shadow factor	0.75 (av)	Strathmann et al., 1995 ⁴⁵ ; Wagholikar et al.,2017 ⁴⁶ ; McGovern et al.,2014 ⁴⁷
Plant life (years), Plant availability	20, 0.9	This study, Sarai Atab et al.2016 ⁴⁸
Interest rate (%)	12	Towler et al., 2022 ⁴⁹ ; Smith, 2005 ⁵⁰
Target extraction capacity (Li ₂ CO ₃ ton/day)	1	This study
Membrane replacement factor (%)	20	El-Dessouky et al., 2002 ⁵¹ ; Strathmann,2004 ⁵²
Li ₂ CO ₃ recovery ratio in precipitation stage (%)	72 (av)	Bukowsky et al.,1997 ²⁹ ; Battaglia et al., 2022 ⁵³ ; Zhao et al.,2019 ⁵⁴ ; Um et al. 2014 ⁵⁵
Li recovery ratio in electrochemical stack (%)	85	This study
Pump efficiency (%)	88	Igor et al., 2008 ⁵⁶
Target Li ₂ CO ₃ purity (%)	≥ 99	Herman, 2018 ⁵⁷ ; Choe, G. et al.,2024 ⁵⁸
Target Li/Mg and Li/Ca mass ratio in Li-rich stream	61	An et al., 2012 ³⁵ ; Zhang et al., 2023 ³⁴ ; Peng et al., 2023 ³⁶
Target Li content in Li-rich stream (ppm)	10,000	Bukowsky et al.,1997 ²⁹ ; Zhao et al.,2019 ⁵⁴ ; Wang et al. 2018 ⁵⁹

Electrochemical process optimization and design parameters. Li brine sources encompass a wide range of compositions and physical properties. Concentrations can range from as low as 0.17 ppm in seawater to as high as ~1100 ppm in brines such as “Salar de Maricunga” (Source Data for Figure 4). The large range of Li concentrations necessitates design optimization for a cost-effective Li recovery process tailored to a specific brine source.

Figure 3A illustrates the concept of cost optimization for Li recovery using electrochemical membrane process. The full set of process equations is included in the supplementary information.

The electrochemical process cost (T_{El}) for a certain production capacity can be expressed as:

$$T_{El} = T_{Li} + T_{an} + T_{st} + T_{pr} + T_{rc} + T_{labor,main} \sim \vec{T}_{S\&M} + \vec{T}_E \quad (\text{eq. 2})$$

Where T_{Li} is the amortized cost of the LiSM investment plus replacement cost, T_{an} is the corresponding term for the anion exchange membrane, T_{st} is the amortized cost of stack capital expenditure and auxiliary equipment, T_{pr} denotes the energy cost related to stack pressure drop, T_{rc} denotes to energy cost from cell resistance and voltage drop, and $T_{labor,main}$ denotes the operational labor and maintenance costs. These components can be grouped into two main terms: $\vec{T}_{S\&M}$ which represents the overall amortized costs related to membrane, hardware, and stack investment, and \vec{T}_E which denotes the sum of costs associated with energy consumption in the electrochemical stack.

$\vec{T}_{S\&M}$ and \vec{T}_E terms in eq. 2 depends, in different functional forms, on four sets of parameters: brine properties, stack and membrane properties, stack design parameters, and economic factors. The optimization procedure returns the design parameters corresponding to minimized cost as a function of the remaining set of parameters, including the concentration of Li in the brine and the price of LiSMs. When other sets of parameters are known, adjusting stack design parameters including h , W/L ratio, and L_f is crucial to minimizing the electrochemical process cost. These parameters collectively control mass transfer and hydrodynamic conditions within the stack. Note that when increasing the required membrane area, there is a simultaneous increase in stack pressure drop and associated energy consumption (Notes S2-S3). Note that throughout this work, the term electrochemical process cost specifically refers to the parameters defined in eq. 2, whereas the term total process cost denotes the sum of the electrochemical process cost and other cost components, including pre-stack intake and pretreatment, brine discharge, and post-stack Li_2CO_3 recovery.

(A)

(B)

Figure 3. Optimization of electrochemical Li recovery process through design parameters.

(A) Illustrates the functionality of the electrochemical process cost considering four sets of parameters: brine properties, stack and membrane characteristics, stack design, and economic parameters. The groups g_1 and g_2 correspond to process-dependent parameters (Ψ_1, Ψ_2, Ψ_3), while f_1 and f_2 represent cost-related functions of economic variables, such as electricity price. Stack design parameters ($h, W/L, L_f$, highlighted in blue) can be adjusted to minimize the electrochemical process cost, assuming the other parameters are fixed.

(B) Exemplifies the impact of deviation from optimal design on energy consumption and electrochemical process cost for Li recovery from seawater. The reported optimal values ($h: 230 \mu\text{m}, W/L: 3477, L_f: 0.92 \text{ mm}$) correspond to the global optimization of the electrochemical process cost as the objective function. In each plot, one design parameter is varied around its optimal value while the other two parameters are held at their global optimum. Assumptions include a Li membrane price of $\$5000/\text{m}^2$ and a Li transference number of 1.

Figure 3B illustrates the impacts of deviation from optimal stack design on the electrochemical process cost for Li recovery from seawater. For all three design parameters, a deviation towards positive values relative to the optimal values results in lower energy consumption due to a reduced pressure drop within the stack. However, the lower energy cost is offset by the increase in required membrane and stack investment. Conversely, a deviation towards negative values leads to a more pronounced increase in energy consumption and therefore overall cost. Among the three design parameters, channel thickness has the greatest impact on process cost, with variations from the optimal value leading to cost increases of up to 1,000% in the negative direction and up to 500% in the positive direction. The W/L ratio ranks second in its impact on cost, while the spacer mesh size has the smallest impact.

Cost analysis of Li_2CO_3 production from diverse brine sources. 25 brines, including seawater, saline lakes, salt flats, geothermal brines, and oilfield brines were categorized into nine groups based on Li concentration. For each group, physical properties- viscosity, density, effective diffusivity, and specific electrical conductivity- were averaged across the brines in that group for use in optimization and cost analysis. For example, the Permian Basin (US) with 22.39 ppm Li, Dead Sea (Israel) with 24.4 ppm Li, and Cerro Prieto (Mexico) with 21.7 ppm Li were combined into the “~22 ppm Li” category, with their physical properties averaged for the cost analysis. The detailed composition and physical properties of all 25 brines are provided in Source Data for Figure 4. Figure 4 and Figure S3 illustrate the electrochemical process costs for the nine groups, along with optimal design parameters at different LiSM prices. Figure 5 and Figure S4 provide the cost breakdown for the overall process, including both electrochemical and non-electrochemical components, along with their cost contributions. The membrane prices cover a wide range of membrane and stack hardware investments, aiding in understanding the cost and energy dynamics

of the process under various scenarios. A stack pressure drop limit of 150 bar was used to allow for variations in the design parameters with minimal constraints, enabling an exploration of their functionality in relation to membrane price and brine concentration. However, the actual pressure drop was often lower than this limit (see next section for further discussion).

The process cost per ton of LCE ranges from approximately \$2,600 to \$28,000, depending on membrane price and Li concentration (excluding the case of seawater). However, out of the 54 total cases analyzed, which are different combinations of brine compositions and membrane prices, 30 cases showed that the production cost remains below \$5,000 per ton of LCE (Source Data for Figure 5). Analysing various membrane prices and brine concentrations, except for the membrane price of \$500/m², indicates that membrane lifecycle costs (capital expenditure and replacement cost) remain the major cost component of the electrochemical process (Figure 5 and Figure S4). For concentrations below 160 ppm, energy consumption is primarily driven by the need to adjust stack pressure drop. However, once the concentration exceeds this threshold, the voltage drop becomes the dominant factor in energy requirements for electrochemical process. This threshold of 160 ppm also marks a critical "break point," below which electrochemical recovery costs increase sharply. This trend parallels observations in Li recovery from geothermal brines using chemical precipitation, where low-concentration brines (< 250 ppm) were found profitable only at high Li₂CO₃ selling prices exceeding \$70 per kg.⁶⁰ Additionally, we observe a critical Li concentration above which non-electrochemical process costs become significant. This critical concentration ranges from 22 ppm at a membrane price of \$500/m² to 250 ppm at a membrane price of \$20,000/m². These findings provide valuable guidelines for designers, indicating when the optimization focus should shift from electrochemical recovery to other stages of the overall extraction process. Total energy consumption for the extraction process varies widely, ranging

from 5,099 kWh for brine with 710 ppm concentration at a membrane price of \$500/m² to 71,099 kWh for brine with 22 ppm at a membrane price of \$40,000/m² (Source Data for Figure 5).

For brines with a similar average Li concentration, a decrease in channel thickness and spacer mesh size are observed as membrane prices increase. This adjustment in the design parameters aims to improve the limiting current density within the stack and consequently reduce the required LiSM area. The decrease in channel thickness and mesh size increases the stack pressure drop and associated energy costs. However, this effect is mitigated by a gradual increase in the W/L ratio, as shown by the inverse relationship between $[L_f, h]$ and W/L in Figure 4. The simultaneous adjustment of three parameters as a function of membrane price serves to minimize the electrochemical cost when membrane and hardware investment are high.

One potential approach to further reduce the overall process cost is the recovery of other valuable elements, such as Mg, from the Li-depleted stream before its disposal back into the brine source. MgCO₃ is a versatile compound with diverse applications, and its extraction as a byproduct could enhance the techno-economic viability of the electrochemical Li₂CO₃ extraction process. To evaluate the potential economic benefit of such an integrated process, we conducted a TEA assuming identical membrane prices for both the Li ion and Mg ion recovery units and the same precipitation conditions. The analysis was performed for three representative brines with Li concentrations of 41 ppm, 160 ppm, and 411 ppm, combined with Mg/L ratios of 65, 2.4, and 0.058 and membrane prices of \$500, \$5000, and \$12,500 per m². These Mg/L ratios were selected based on actual brine compositions, which will be discussed in subsequent sections. The results showed that, in most cases, there was no significant economic benefit from the recovery of Mg. Only for low-cost membranes and brines with high Mg/Li ratios (~2.4 and ~65) did the recovery of Mg offer potential improvements in the overall TEA of the Li₂CO₃ extraction process (see Note S11 in

the supplementary information). This outcome is primarily due to the significantly lower market price of MgCO_3 , which limits the economic gains from its recovery, leaving little or no benefit for the primary Li_2CO_3 extraction process.

Impact of larger plant capacity. We also evaluated production costs for larger plant capacities of 10 ton of LCE per day and 100 ton of LCE per day, using a representative brine containing 41 ppm Li and a membrane price of \$5,000/m². Design parameters shifted with scale: channel thickness and filament size showed only minor changes, whereas the W/L ratio increased sharply- from 61 at 1 ton per day, to 540 at 10 ton per day, and to 6,194 at 100 ton per day (see Table S4 in the supplementary information). This rise in W/L ratio reflects the optimization process aimed at mitigating the substantial stack pressure adjustment costs associated with low Li concentration and the high feed volumes required. Larger plants were also more sensitive to deviations from optimal design parameters. For instance, increasing channel thickness by 20% above the optimal value raised total process costs by 46% at 1 ton of LCE per day capacity, but by 67% at 100 ton of LCE per day capacity (see Figure S9 in the supplementary information). These findings highlight that at higher capacities, the delicate balance between energy consumption and membrane investment becomes increasingly critical.

Figure 4. Electrochemical process cost for various brine sources and different Li membrane prices.

The figure illustrates the electrochemical process cost for producing 1 ton of LCE per day along with optimal design parameters. Data are presented based on the minimum cost obtained from optimal design parameters for each combination of brine source and Li membrane price. Brines are grouped based on their Li concentration, and other physical properties (viscosity, density, effective diffusivity, and specific electrical conductivity) were averaged within each group for analysis. Details of the brine data can be found in the Source Data for Figure 4. Assumptions include a Li transference number of 1 and stack pressure drop limit of 150 bar. Data for additional membrane prices are presented in Figure S3.

Li Membrane Price: 500 (USD)/m²

Li Membrane Price: 2500 (USD)/m²

Li Membrane Price: 5000 (USD)/m²

Li Membrane Price: 12500 (USD)/m²

Figure 5. Cost analysis of Li₂CO₃ production (1 ton of LCE per day) through an optimized electrochemical Li recovery process.

The bubble plots show how different cost components of Li₂CO₃ production vary with membrane price and brine Li concentration. Each column corresponds to a specific Li concentration and each row to a distinct cost component. Within each column, bubble size is proportional to that component's contribution for the given brine. For visual clarity, seawater-related costs were scaled down by a factor of 200, and costs for other brines were scaled down by a factor of 5 prior to plotting. For example, for seawater at a membrane price of 500 USD/m², the total process cost is 200×2200 USD per ton of LCE, while for a brine with 22 ppm Li at the same membrane price it is 5×1030 USD per ton of LCE. Other components in each column can be scaled using the same factors. The right-hand subplots show the percentage contribution of each component for the corresponding membrane price. The costs associated with stack pressure drop adjustment and cell resistance reflect the overall energy consumption of the electrochemical process (measured in kWh multiplied by the energy price). Assumptions include a Li transference number of 1 and stack pressure drop limit of 150 bar. Data for additional membrane prices are presented in Figure S4. Detailed values of costs and energy consumption can be found in Source Data for Figure 5.

Impact of pressure drop limit on electrochemical process optimization. ED stacks are typically engineered to accommodate a pressure drop range of 0.2 to 5 bar. This design standard suits ED desalination processes, where cation concentrations can reach up to e.g. 15,000 ppm.^{39, 61, 62} However, Li recovery targets significantly lower concentration ranges. Due to the high-volume rate to be processed, operating at low pressure drops imposes constraints on flow velocity and cell design. These constraints result in an unoptimized mass transfer coefficient and lowered operational limiting current density. In this work, the stack pressure drop limit represents the maximum feed stream pressure that the electrochemical stack can handle, assuming the outlet is at atmospheric condition. Figure 6A illustrates how the constraint on stack pressure drop limit affects the membrane requirement for different brine groups. As the pressure drop limit decreases, there is a corresponding increase in the required membrane area, which becomes more pronounced for brines with lower Li concentration. It is important to note that the actual operating pressure drop for optimal conditions does not always reach the stack pressure drop limit. Across all cases investigated (including variations in membrane price and feed composition), 94% of cases had an operating pressure drop below 81 bar, and 84% of cases had an operating pressure drop at or below 33 bar (see Source Data for Figure 6). Within the explored range of stack pressure drop limits, there is a specific threshold where a significant reduction in required membrane area occurs. This behavior underscores another crucial factor, referred to as membrane saving efficiency (Figure 6B). While operating pressure drops above 80 bar result in an average reduction of 0.01 (m²/kWh)/bar, pressure drop ranges below 20 bar exhibit a reduction range of 0.1 up to 0.9 (m²/kWh)/bar. Figure 6C illustrates the electrochemical process cost as a function of the stack pressure drop limits for three representative brine groups. The heightened impact of pressure drop limit on cost reduction is evident at lower ranges of pressure drops for all three brines.

Note that operating the electrochemical process at higher levels of pressure drop, specifically above 5 bar, would require the development of new stacks designed to handle elevated pressure drops, rather than relying on existing ED equipment. This necessitates adapting stack hardware and housing materials, typically made from thermoplastics in ED systems,^{39, 63} to more robust materials, such as fiber-reinforced plastic (FRP), capable of withstanding elevated pressure drops like those used in RO and high-pressure ultrafiltration systems.^{64, 65} For example, bipolar membrane ED stacks capable of operating at pressures up to 20 bar for CO₂ desorption have already been patented, demonstrating the viability of high-pressure stack design.⁶⁶ These modifications could increase capital expenditure, potentially impacting overall process costs.

(A)

(B)

(C)

Li membrane price (USD/ m^2): 5000, 12500, 20000, 40000

Figure 6 . The impact of stack pressure drop limit on electrochemical process performance and cost.

(A) Illustrates the impact of stack pressure drop limit on the required amount of LiSM for eight brine groups.
(B) Represents the membrane area/energy consumption ratio as a function of Li concentration and stack pressure drop limit, with the color scale indicating the membrane savings efficiency. The subplot (right) focuses on the process condition where the highest impact of operative pressure drop on membrane savings can be obtained.
(C) Shows the impact of the stack pressure drop limit on the electrochemical process cost for three representative brines, using an 8-bar pressure drop limit as the reference case. All data are derived from an optimal process for production of 1 ton of LCE per day assuming a Li transference number of 1. Note that the actual operative pressure drop might be less than the stack's pressure drop limit. The liquid at the outlet of the feed stream is assumed to be at atmospheric condition. The cost reduction percentages shown are averaged across different membrane prices. More detailed information is available in the Source Data for Figure 6.

Recovery ratio and design flexibility. In addition to stack design characteristics, two key process variables in the electrochemical recovery stage- recovery ratio and current density- can be adjusted to further affect electrochemical process performance. The current density is capped at the limiting current, which defines the maximum operative current (see Methods). A reduction in the total current density, as a fraction of the limiting current, leads to a decrease in energy costs associated with cell resistance. The effects of operating at a fraction of the limiting current were evaluated for a representative brine with a Li concentration of 41 ppm, considering a range of membrane prices (\$500–\$20,000/m²). Generally, decreasing the current density resulted in higher overall process costs (Figure S5A). Analysis of the data revealed that while reducing current density lowers energy costs associated with cell resistance and voltage drop, it also increases energy costs to compensate for the higher pressure drop, which is caused by the longer flow path length. Additionally, higher capital expenditures were required to accommodate the increased membrane area needed to maintain the same extraction capacity. Therefore, the economic benefit of operating at a reduced limiting current density depends on both membrane price and brine composition. Specifically, for lower-cost membranes and higher Li concentrations- where the costs to compensate for the pressure drop are less significant- operating at a reduced limiting current density can offer cost advantages by reducing energy expenses related to cell resistance and voltage drop.

As discussed in preceding sections, minimized production cost is sometimes observed at pressure drops exceeding 5 bar, which surpasses the current stack tolerance. Stack design modifications such as increasing the W/L ratio, channel thickness, and mesh size are potential strategies to reduce pressure drop. However, these changes lead to increased electrochemical process costs because of deviation from optimal design, as demonstrated in Figure 3. Alternatively, operating at lower recovery ratios offers the potential for reduced ranges of pressure drop and decreased process costs (Figures 7 and S5B). The primary effect of operating at a lower recovery ratio is an increase in the limiting current and a reduction in the required membrane area. This reduction in membrane area can be addressed through two potential design adjustments: 1) increasing W/L ratio of the stack (while keeping h and L_f constant), and 2) increasing h and L_f (while maintaining a constant W/L ratio). These adjustments result in both lower electrochemical process costs and reduced operative pressure drop (Figure 7). Conversely, if no changes are made to the stack design parameters while reducing membrane area through lower recovery ratios, there will be an increase in both pressure drop and process cost (Figure S6). The minimum cost observed at specific recovery ratios is because of the trade-off between reduced electrochemical process costs and increased intake, pretreatment, and brine disposal costs associated with operating at lower recovery ratios. This finding underscores the importance of carefully evaluating intake, pretreatment, and brine disposal costs when targeting lower recovery ratios. Nevertheless, the ability to lower operating pressure drop through reduced recovery ratios represents a critical process design consideration, particularly considering the uncertainties surrounding the capital expenses required for stack designs that can tolerate higher pressure drops.

Figure 7. Recovery ratio and its impact on pressure drop and process costs.

(A) Illustration of potential stack design modifications associated with reduced membrane area (A_m) and changes in pressure drop (ΔP) when operating at lower recovery ratios. Designs *a* and *b* result in both reduced membrane area and lower pressure drop, while design *c* leads to a decrease in membrane area but an increase in pressure drop.

(B) Shows the impact of reduced recovery ratios on process costs and pressure drop for a representative brine with 41 ppm Li and a membrane price of \$12,500/m². Left: increasing h and L_f while maintaining a constant W/L ratio. Right: increasing the W/L ratio while keeping h and L_f constant.

Ca and Mg leakage. The key concept of Li-SICs is primarily based on the mechanism of fast Li diffusion. Combined with a percolation radius in the range of 0.5 to 0.7 angstroms,⁶⁷ this mechanism provides a unique opportunity for achieving a high migration selectivity for Li ions, as discussed in Figure 1. However, the relative prevalence of other ions in the brine, such as Ca and Mg, is not factored into the migration selectivity term. It is therefore crucial to consider the impact of potential deviations from a Li transference number of 1, particularly for brines with elevated Ca and Mg concentrations.

The overall flux selectivity between Li and other ions (J_{Li}/J_i) is a product of sorption selectivity ($S_{sorption}$) and migration selectivity ($S_{migration}$)^{68, 69}:

$$S_{Li/i} \equiv \frac{J_{Li}}{J_i} \approx S_{sorption} \times S_{migration} = \frac{K_{Li} \times C_{Li,b}}{K_i \times C_{i,b}} \times \frac{j_{Li}}{j_i} \quad (\text{eq. 3, where } i = \text{Ca}^{2+}, \text{Mg}^{2+}, \text{etc.})$$

Sorption selectivity is a function of the relative ion concentrations in the brine (C_{Li}/C_i) and the relative sorption coefficients (K_{Li}/K_i). The sorption coefficient for a specific ion is influenced by the Donnan potential and ion activity coefficients in the membrane phase and solution phase.⁷⁰ Activity coefficients are also influenced by corresponding salt concentration in the solution phase. Thus, the sorption selectivity term becomes a critical factor when dealing with brines that have elevated Ca and Mg concentrations

Figure 8A shows the distribution of Mg and Ca across the brines considered in this work. The data reveals a diverse range of Li/Ca and Li/Mg ratios across different Li feed concentrations. For example, within the brine group with an average Li concentration of 41 ppm, various Li/Mg weight ratios (0.015, 0.42, and 17.27) and corresponding Li/Ca ratios (0.00147, 0.08, and 0.15) are observed. Figure 8B examines the impact of deviations from a Li transference number of 1, specifically focusing on low selectivity values for these representative compositions. Lower

selectivity values require the implementation of additional electrochemical recovery stages (see Note S4 in the supplementary information), which varies depending on the membrane selectivities and brine compositions (Source Data for Figure 8).

For representative brines low in divalent cations ($\text{Li}/(\text{Mg}+\text{Ca}) \sim 0.15$) and representative brines with a medium range of divalent cations ($\text{Li}/(\text{Ca}+\text{Mg}) \sim 0.067$), energy consumption in the electrochemical process can increase by 170% to 350% at selectivities ~ 22 , and can rise further to 935% at lower selectivities ~ 5 , relative to a scenario with a Li transference number of 1. The increase in required membrane area is lower compared to energy consumption, ranging from 30% at selectivities ~ 22 to 120% at lower selectivities ~ 5 . For representative brines with high $\text{Li}/(\text{divalent cations})$ ratio (in Figure 8B, brine with $\text{Li}/\text{Mg} \sim 17.12$, and assuming no Ca leakage), the impact of selectivity is very small. The significant impact on energy consumption as a function of membrane selectivities results from the increase in overall current density and cell voltage costs rather than stack pressure drop. For detailed values on energy costs associated with cell resistance and voltage drop, see the Source Data for Figure 8. For brines rich in Ca and Mg ($\text{Li}/(\text{Ca}+\text{Mg}) \sim 0.0014$), the increase in energy consumption can range from $2\times$ up to $270\times$. Note that across different compositions, the impact on increased membrane area and energy consumption becomes increasingly significant when selectivity is below 11.

(B)

- Change in required Li membrane area due to Mg leakage
- ▼— Change in energy consumption due to Mg leakage
- Change in required Li membrane area due to Mg and Ca leakage
- ▼-- Change in energy consumption due to Mg and Ca leakage

Li/Mg: 17.27, Li/Ca: 0.15, Li/(Ca+Mg): 0.149

Li/Mg: 0.42, Li/Ca: 0.08, Li/(Ca+Mg): 0.067

Li/Mg: 0.0154, Li/Ca: 0.00147, Li/(Ca+Mg): 0.0013

Figure 8. Variation in Ca and Mg distribution across brines and their impact on electrochemical Li recovery.

(A) Illustrates diversity in Li/Ca and Li/Mg ratios for brines of different Li concentrations analyzed in this study, highlighting the importance of selectivity in the LiSM. Each color set corresponds to a brine with a specific Li concentration, while triangles and circles represent the Li/Ca and Li/Mg ratios, respectively, for that brine.

(B) Presents relative changes in required membrane area and energy consumption for electrochemical process in Li recovery from three representative brines with similar Li concentrations ($C_{\text{Li}} \sim 41$ ppm) but covering different Li/Ca and Li/Mg ratios, demonstrating the sensitivity of process cost to brine composition and selectivity deviations. Two scenarios were considered: one with only Mg leakage and the other with both Mg and Ca leakages from the same

brine. The colors for subplot titles are adopted from the corresponding brines in (A). Details of brine compositions and Li membrane selectivities can be found in the Source Data for Figure 8.

Operational and durability challenges. A phenomenon not addressed in this study is the possible variations in current utilization under different operating conditions, independent of the inherent Li/Mg and Li/Ca selectivity of the membrane. Li concentration gradient between the feed and recovery streams acts as a thermodynamic driving force, which can lead to Li leakage as a co-ion, thereby reducing current utilization.⁷¹ Current utilization affected by co-ion leakage is influenced by factors such as hydrodynamics, salt concentration, and operating current.^{72, 73} These dynamics highlight the importance of future experimental studies or molecular dynamics simulations to evaluate Li leakage across various conditions. Such investigations are critical for quantifying the additional membrane area and energy consumption required at lower values of current utilization. Assessing long-term membrane selectivity and durability using realistic brine compositions is crucial for accurately evaluating the cost-effectiveness of Li recovery from brines rich in divalent ions. Natural brines exhibit wide variability in composition and physical properties, which can significantly affect membrane performance and lifespan. Such variability directly influences both the required pre-treatment steps and key operational parameters, including the membrane replacement factor (MRF). In this study, we evaluated the impact of membrane lifetime on process cost for a representative brine containing 41 ppm Li, considering membrane prices of \$500 and \$12,500/m² (results are provided in Figure S8 in the supplementary information). Increasing the MRF from the baseline value of 0.2 (equivalent to a 5-year membrane lifetime) to 0.9 (approximately 1.2 years membrane lifetime) increased total process costs by about 5% at the lower membrane price and up to 80% at the higher price, underscoring the critical role of membrane durability in process economics. These findings support the need for experimental

validation of LiSMs' performance using actual brines and emphasize the value of such data for guiding potential adjustments to pre-treatment processes. Furthermore, understanding the long-term performance of LiSM is essential for evaluating the trade-off between the Li used in membrane fabrication and the net Li recovered over the membrane's operational life. The Li content in the membrane must be economically justified by the amount of Li it enables to be recovered.

Additionally, some studies have reported leakage of Na to a certain extent. For example, Li et al. reported a Li/Na binary selectivity of approximately 16,000 using a perovskite-type $\text{Li}_{0.33}\text{La}_{0.56}\text{TiO}_3$ SIC,¹⁴ which corresponds to 2% Na leakage during Li recovery from seawater. While this degree of Na leakage may not significantly impact the Li_2CO_3 recovery stage, its impact on the cell voltage needs to be considered, as previously discussed in the context of Mg and Ca leakage.

Finally, although electrochemical Li recovery can be powered by renewable electricity and operated at room temperature, there remain environmental concerns regarding the freshwater consumption required for the extract stream. Assuming a target Li concentration of 10,000 ppm in the extract stream, producing one ton of LCE would require approximately 19 m³ of freshwater. This demand can pose a challenge in arid regions. A possible approach to reduce water use is to optimize the process to achieve higher Li concentrations in the extract stream, thereby lowering the overall freshwater requirement. Achieving this will require membranes capable of minimizing co-ion leakage under high concentration gradients, as discussed above. In addition, as noted by Vera et al.,²⁴ other environmental impacts from Li extraction should be monitored during exploitation, as some effects may only become apparent over extended operation.

Model key assumptions and sensitivity analysis. The mass-transport correlations applied in this work are based on the seminal studies of Isaacson and Sonin,⁷⁴ Kuroda et al.,⁷⁵ and Wright et al.,⁷⁶ who developed and experimentally validated these relationships for electro dialysis systems. The specific correlations used under different operating regimes are detailed in the supplementary information Note S2. In their original form, these correlations relate the mass-transfer coefficient to the Reynolds (Re) and Schmidt (Sc) numbers, typically under limiting-current conditions. It is important to note that these correlations were primarily developed for single-salt or binary electrolyte systems. In contrast, Li recovery from natural brines often involves complex multi-cation compositions, where hydrodynamics, ion-pairing, and competitive transport effects could cause deviations from the established forms of these correlations. Consequently, the applicability of these correlations to actual brine conditions must be considered an assumption in our baseline model. To assess the potential influence of this assumption on process design and economics, we conducted a sensitivity analysis in which the multiplicative coefficient (f) and the Reynolds-number exponent (g) in the Sherwood correlations were varied in the general form:

$$Sh \sim f \times Re^g \times Sc^{1/3} \quad (\text{eq. 4})$$

f and g were each perturbed by $\pm 10\%$ and $\pm 20\%$ from their nominal values to quantify their impact on key stack design parameters and the electrochemical process cost (results are detailed in the supplementary information Note S13 and Table S5). The results show that process performance is more sensitive to changes in the Reynolds-number exponent (g) than to changes in the multiplicative factor (f). For example, a +20% increase in g led to a 53% reduction in the electrochemical process cost, whereas a -20% change resulted in a 40% cost increase. In comparison, equivalent +20% and -20% variations in f resulted in only a 14% cost decrease and a 20% cost increase, respectively. These trends underscore the critical importance of accurately

determining the Re exponent for realistic brine conditions. Overall, this analysis highlights the need for dedicated experimental studies to establish mass-transfer correlations under the specific hydrodynamic and compositional conditions encountered in Li recovery from natural brines.

Conclusions

Electrochemical Li recovery through the selective ED process offers several advantages over other Li extraction technologies. Compared to solar evaporation, which typically achieves Li recovery rates of 50-70% over 12-24 months and results in significant water loss,²⁴ membrane-based ED achieves more than 90% Li recovery with controllable extraction rates,¹⁴ minimal water consumption, and the potential for brine reinjection. Adsorption and ion-exchange processes also provide high recovery, but require chemical regeneration using acid and base solutions, resulting in considerable reagent consumption and waste generation.⁷⁷ While solvent extraction (SX) offers excellent selectivity, especially in high Mg/Li ratio brines, it involves the use of organic solvents and remains at the pilot stage for Li recovery applications.⁷⁸ Selective ED requires approximately 7-15 kWh per cubic meter of brine processed,⁷⁹ placing it within the typical energy range of other direct Li extraction (DLE) technologies, and it offers low chemical consumption and operational flexibility. This process, especially when coupled with highly selective membranes such as Li-SICs, yields a high-purity LiCl stream suitable for direct precipitation of battery-grade Li₂CO₃. Additionally, selective ED is modular, scalable, and avoids the environmental impacts associated with evaporation ponds (e.g., land use and water loss) and solvent-based processes.

Building on these performance and sustainability benefits, the present study focused on the role of key design parameters in the electrochemical membrane Li recovery stage- including channel thickness, width-to-length ratio of the flow path, and spacer mesh size- and investigated their simultaneous optimization to minimize product costs. While the W/L ratio can be adjusted through

different flow pattern arrangements during operation, channel thickness and spacer mesh size are dependent on the stack manufacturer's design. The optimization framework presented in this study enables tailoring of the system to accommodate variations in the brine feed compositions and material costs.

Based on optimization analyses, we found that Li_2CO_3 production from seawater requires substantial energy input, with approximately 4420 MWh consumed for stack pressure drop adjustment (considering 150 bar as stack pressure drop limit) and about 595 MWh for the intake and pretreatment stage per ton of LCE, making the process challenging from an energy and therefore economical perspective. There is a significant decrease in electrochemical process costs for brine groups with average Li concentrations ranging from 22 ppm to 160 ppm, with costs reducing by 80% averaged over various membrane prices. Beyond 160 ppm, the cost reduction is less pronounced and less sensitive to design variations, averaging around 33% reduction as Li concentration increases from 160 ppm up to 710 ppm. Therefore, the adaptability of stack design becomes more important for cost savings for brine sources with Li concentrations below 160 ppm.

The study also revealed the importance of the stack pressure drop limit on the cost-effectiveness of the electrochemical process. A noticeable cost reduction was observed as a result of increased membrane saving efficiency at operating pressure drops in the range of 8-30 bar. The findings highlight the role of stack design and manufacturing in tailoring the maximum pressure drop that the stack can handle within the lower ranges of pressure drop limits, potentially leading to significant cost savings for lower Li concentrations and more expensive membranes.

A potential strategy for maintaining lower ranges of pressure drop while minimizing production cost was found to be a reduction in the recovery ratio. This approach enabled operation at higher limiting current densities, a reduction in the required membrane area and allowed for adjustments

to stack characteristics to lower pressure drops. These adjustments included increasing the W/L ratio or using higher values for channel thickness and spacer mesh size. The strategy introduced the recovery ratio as a process variable, in addition to stack characteristics, to optimize both process cost and operating pressure drop.

Despite the promising performance of LiSMs such as Li-SICs reported in the literature, this work also considered scenarios with low selectivity ranges, coupled with concurrent leakages of Ca and Mg (binary selectivities ranging from 1600 down to 5). The findings indicated that operating at low selectivity values significantly impacts the energy consumption of the electrochemical recovery stage, thereby making the cell voltage drop a major energy and cost component of the process. The results highlighted the critical importance of achieving high selectivities, particularly when targeting brines with elevated concentrations of Ca and Mg. Failure to maintain high selectivity can substantially impact overall cost perspectives, even with the most optimized design. Future work should include performance testing and durability assessments of Li-selective membranes at elevated Mg and Ca concentrations, as encountered in a broad range of brines. Additionally, future experimental efforts to refine mass transport correlations under high flow velocities and elevated salinities are recommended to improve the models under limiting current conditions and across varying operational parameters.

Methods

Operation at limiting current density. To evaluate the electrochemical process, operation at limiting current density was considered. At the limiting current density, the concentration of counter ions near the membrane surface becomes very low because the ion transport from the bulk to the membrane becomes slower than the transport across the membrane. This depletion creates a steep concentration gradient, which enhances the driving force for further counter-ion transport.⁶¹

Limiting current density is considered a critical design parameter which determines the efficiency of an ED plant.⁸⁰ Operating at near limiting current density ensures that the membrane's ion-exchange capacity is fully utilized, leading to maximized Li recovery efficiency (per unit of membrane area). Exceeding this limiting current will no longer result in additional Li recovery, but it may induce secondary phenomena such as water dissociation and the transport of other ions through the membrane.⁸¹ These effects have the potential to deteriorate the performance of the LiSMs over time, leading to a loss of selectivity. In commercial ED and EDR systems, a value of 70-80% of the limiting current is used to provide a desired level of safety in system design.⁸²

Under limiting current conditions, the recovery rate is independent of cell voltage and is determined by the Li transport rate from the center of the channel (well-mixed bulk solution) to the membrane-solution interface:

$$i_{lim} = (Z_{Li} \cdot F) \times \left(\frac{D_{Li}}{D_{eff}} \right) \times K_{eff} \times C_{Li}^{av.f.m} \quad (\text{eq. 5})$$

Where K_{eff} is the mass transport coefficient expressed based on multi-ion diffusivity of the brine (m/s), and $C_{Li}^{av.f.m}$ is the log-mean Li molar concentration in the feed stream (mol/m³).⁸³ The other symbols have their usual meanings (see Table S1 for nomenclature). The Li recovery is a result of

differences in the transference numbers of Li and other cations in the LiSM. The total current is related to the limiting current density through the Li transference number:

$$i_t = i_{lim}/t_{Li} \quad (\text{eq. 6})$$

Where t_{Li} denotes the Li transference number in the LiSM. When the LiSM is only selective to Li, t_{Li} is equal to one, and the total current is equivalent to limiting current. However, when there are leakages of other cations, the total current is larger than limiting current due to deviation of Li transference number from unity. Under these conditions, the partial current related to other cations can be evaluated through their corresponding transference numbers:

$$i_i = t_i \cdot i_t \quad (\text{eq. 7})$$

Where i_i and t_i denote the partial current and transference number of cation i in the LiSM, respectively.

Electrochemical process cost (T_{EI}) as the objective function. Operation under limiting current conditions allow for various process segments to be linked through design parameters. Increasing the limiting current density reduces the required membrane area and the capital expenditure of the stack investment for a given recovery rate. This adjustment can be done by increasing the mass transport coefficient in the boundary layer, which is determined by the hydrodynamic flow conditions, a function of the flow velocity and the stack design characteristics. Improving these hydrodynamic conditions simultaneously will increase the pressure drop in the stack, which must be overcome using circulation pumps. Additionally, adjusting the stack design will also influence the cell voltage cost (see Notes S2-S3 in the supplementary information).

Accordingly, in this work, the electrochemical process cost was considered as the objective function based on the sum of the conflicting material and energy cost factors centered around the

concept of limiting current density. Formulas for evaluating the electrochemical process cost, based on the various terms in eq. 2, are derived and described in detail in the supplementary information.

Optimization process. The Li recovery process was formulated as a nonlinear programming (NLP) problem aimed at minimizing the total cost of extraction per ton of Li_2CO_3 produced per day. In addition to the electrochemical process cost (eq. 2), the objective function also included the costs associated with brine intake, pretreatment, and disposal, particularly in scenarios where the recovery ratio was treated as a decision variable. The objective function in this study encapsulates complex nonlinearities resulting from mass transfer, fluid dynamics, and capital amortization. Specifically, it includes exponential, logarithmic, and power-law terms derived from both physical principles and empirical correlations (details in supplementary information, Note S1). To handle these nonlinearities, the optimization was implemented in MATLAB (R2019b) using the `fmincon` solver from the Optimization Toolbox, employing the interior-point algorithm.⁸⁴

⁸⁵ This approach supports both nonlinear objective functions and nonlinear inequality/equality constraints. The general syntax of the solver is:

```
x = fmincon(fun, x0, A, b, Aeq, beq, lb, ub, nonlcon)
```

Here, `x0` is the initial guess vector; `lb` and `ub`, respectively, define lower and upper bounds on the design variables, ensuring that the solution lies within the feasible design space ($lb \leq x \leq ub$).

Constraints are defined as:

Linear equalities: $A_{eq} \cdot x = b_{eq}$

Linear inequalities: $A \cdot x \leq b$

Nonlinear constraints: $c(x) \leq 0$, $ceq(x) = 0$ (defined in the `nonlcon` function)

The model included three free input variables:

h: Channel thickness of the electrochemical stack (m)

L_f: Spacer filament size (m)

W/L: Ratio of width to length of the flow path (dimensionless)

Nonlinear inequality constraints were implemented through a custom constraint function (nonlcon) to ensure:

- The pressure drop across the stack remained below pressure drop limit
- The spacer mesh size (defined as $\Delta x = L_f/h$) remained within literature-reported bounds ($2 \leq \Delta x \leq 31$, for more information see Source Data for Figure 4)

Since no linear equality or inequality constraints applied, A, b, Aeq, and beq were passed as empty arrays. The optimization was executed using the following command:

```
[xopt , fopt , exitflag , output] = fmincon(@objective, x0, [], [], [], [], lb, ub, @nonlcon)
```

Where $x_{opt} = [h, L_f, \frac{W}{L}]$ is the optimal design configuration, f_{opt} is the minimized process cost, $exitflag$ indicates solver termination status (positive values confirm successful outcome), and $output$ is a structure with information about the optimization process.

The optimal solution x_{opt} was used to compute additional outputs such as membrane area, flow velocity (u), and detailed cost breakdowns. All initial guesses (x_0) were sampled from within the feasible design space (defined by ub and lb). Details of the constraints and boundaries of design variables are provided in Note S6 of the supplementary information.

Due to the potential non-convexity of the problem, for all optimization practices a multi-start strategy was adopted to improve robustness against convergence to local minima. A custom MATLAB script generated 10,000 initial guess vectors $[x_0]$, uniformly distributed within the

feasible design space. Each of these was independently optimized using `fmincon`. The solution yielding the lowest total cost was selected as the baseline optimal solution. In addition to the baseline solution, the model retained all solutions within 2-5% of the minimum cost. These near-optimal solutions were subjected to a post-optimization screening step, which applied engineering feasibility criteria including constraints on Reynolds number (Re), flow velocity (u), total flow path length (L), and membrane rupture threshold ($\Delta p_{max,m}$). These criteria, based on literature thresholds, ensured that the selected designs were not only cost-effective but also practically viable (details can be found in the supplementary information, Note S6). This step ensured that the selected design was both computationally robust and operationally feasible. Post-screening was required for only four edge cases involving low Li concentrations (0.17-22 ppm) and expensive membranes (20,000-40,000 USD/m²); all other cases were resolved within the main optimization process. A flow diagram illustrating the optimization and screening process is provided in the supplementary information, Note S10.

To validate the global optimality of the multi-start solutions, a hybrid optimization approach was performed using MATLAB's `surrogateopt` solver. This method explores the design space globally using surrogate modeling and identifies promising regions. The best surrogate solution was further refined using `fmincon`, starting from that point. Six representative cases (Li concentrations: 0.17 ppm, 41 ppm, and 710 ppm; membrane prices: 500 and 40,000 USD/m²) were examined and the results are presented in Table S2 in the supplementary information. The hybrid optimization yielded solutions that closely matched the multi-start baseline, confirming its validity as a near-global optimum.

A sensitivity analysis was performed to assess the impact of key design variables on the total process cost and to validate the robustness of the optimization results. For each brine case, two

contour plots were generated: in the first, h was fixed at its optimal value, while W and L_f were varied; in the second, W was held constant at its optimized value, while h and L_f were varied. This analysis was conducted for three representative cases, covering three brine Li concentrations (0.17 ppm, 41 ppm, and 710 ppm) at a membrane cost of 12,500 USD/m². The resulting cost landscapes, visualized in supplementary information, confirmed that the optimal configurations identified by the NLP routine consistently aligned with cost minima. Full contour plots and sensitivity data are provided in Note S9 and Figure S7 in the supplementary information.

The range of prices for the LiSM was considered according to the current market price and the expected technological maturation in the future. Only spacers with an attack angle of 90° were considered, as there was a lack of valid mass transport correlation within the explored range of Reynolds numbers for other types of spacers. Inequality constraints were considered within the performance limit reported in the literature to obtain solutions with realistic process conditions (see Note S6 and Source Data for Figure 4). Under scenarios of lower selectivity and requirements for additional recovery stages, the optimization process was performed for all follow-up recovery stages with no manipulation of the size or conditions of the stage. A separate MATLAB script was used to obtain physical properties and Li concentration for nine representative brines, covering the full range of single data points discussed in the Source Data for Figure 4.

The analysis of the brine compositions (Source Data for Figure 4) indicates that, except for the geothermal brine at Cesano, Italy, the Cl/SO₄ molar ratio in other brines is greater than unity, ranging from 7.22 in Searles Lake to approximately 6500 in the Salton Sea. Assuming equal permselectivity for Cl⁻ and SO₄²⁻, this range in brine compositions results in Li/SO₄ molar ratios between ~15 and ~13000 in the Li-rich stream. Additionally, relatively pure Li₂CO₃ can be obtained at ~80.5% recovery with a minimum Li/SO₄ molar ratio of 2.⁸⁶ These considerations

support the assumption of Cl^- being the major counter-anion during electrochemical process optimization.

Various studies have reported high purity Li_2CO_3 precipitation under experimental conditions with high Li/Ca and Li/Mg weight ratios. For example, Li_2CO_3 extraction has been achieved from treated solutions with [Li/Mg \sim 130, Li/Ca \sim 60, purity \sim 99.92%],³⁴ [Li/Mg \sim 60, Li/Ca \sim 400, purity \sim 99.55%],³⁵ and [Li/Mg \sim 34, Li/Ca not provided, purity \sim 98.5%]³⁶. In contrast, a decrease in purity down to 90% was reported when the Li/Mg ratio dropped to \sim 20.⁵³ These reports cover a wide and disparate range of Li-to-divalent cation ratios, which makes it difficult to draw definitive correlations between Li_2CO_3 purity and Li/Ca or Li/Mg ratios. Thus, in this study, a lower limit of [Li/Ca, and Li/Mg \sim 61] was considered to ensure a purity of over 99%. We acknowledge that the substantial impact of binary selectivity on process economics warrants further investigation. Future studies should systematically explore a broader and more carefully controlled range of Li/Ca and Li/Mg ratios to establish clearer guidelines and potentially reduce the performance requirements for LiSMs.

The data for AEMs were sourced from Fumasep membranes, which are widely used in electrochemical systems and electrodialysis.⁸⁷⁻⁸⁹ The specifications for these membranes, along with those for LiSMs, are detailed in the Source Data for Figure 4. To account for variability in membrane properties, the average value for area resistance was calculated across available datasets and used in the model. This approach ensures the modeling assumptions remain generalized and not overly reliant on specific membrane type. However, since most current LiSMs fall into the category of inorganic membranes, their actual resistance in aqueous media may vary. Membrane resistance becomes a critical factor when cell voltage contributes significantly to the overall system costs. As discussed in this manuscript, this is particularly relevant for brines with higher Li

concentrations and scenarios involving more expensive membranes. For the AEM, a complete permselectivity for the Cl anion was assumed and for LiSMs the range of binary selectivities were adopted from literature data (see Source Data for Figure 8).

Zero trans-membrane pressure. To prevent water transport, membrane rupture, and water flux through the ion exchange membranes, identical operating pressure drop was applied to both the feed and recovery streams (Note S3). It is important to note that maintaining identical pressure drops across the stack requires careful system design and may introduce additional capital and operational expenditures, which are beyond the scope of this study.

Width-to-length ratio adjustment. The width-to-length ratio in the process can be managed through flow patterns. The overall width-to-length ratio can be adjusted using the following equations:

$$\frac{W}{L} = \frac{\sum n_j \cdot w}{\sum n_i \cdot l} \quad (\text{eq.8}), \quad A = W \cdot L \quad (\text{eq. 9})$$

where n_j is the number of cell pairs in parallel, and n_i is the number of cell pairs in series within the same recovery stage. The variables w and l represent the width and length of individual membranes, respectively, as provided by the stack or membrane supplier. The variables W and L represent the total width and total length of the membrane, respectively, and A represents the total membrane area.

The scheme above illustrates this concept. The same overall membrane area can be arranged to achieve different W/L ratios by adjusting the number of cell pairs in parallel and series configurations. In the example above, the length and width of individual membranes are considered to be equal.

Non-electrochemical stages. Based on the fixed temperature-driven conditions of the Li-rich stream, the chemical recovery stage was treated as a fixed cost (Note S4). The costs for the intake, pre-treatment and brine disposal were dependent on the source distance and the feed volumetric flow rate, the latter being a function of brine Li concentration for a given production rate. For Li recovery from seawater in this work, an offshore distance of 500 meters and an average depth of 10 meters below the sea surface were considered (Note S1).^{37, 40} Though for seawater the source location was influential, for other sources, intake cost and the distance from the brine source were less significant due to their much higher Li concentrations. We acknowledge that different total dissolved salinities and compositions of various brine feeds may necessitate changes in the standard pre-treatment procedures; however, identifying these changes will require future experimental approaches employing LiSMs and various actual brine compositions.

Data availability

The current study is based on a comprehensive electrochemical model developed from literature-reported parameters and detailed evaluation of mass transport under varying hydrodynamic conditions. All modeling steps in the optimization procedure, and other supporting results are fully described through Equations S1-S77 and Notes S1-S13 in the supplementary information. Brine compositions, membrane characteristics, and other relevant parameters used in the model are provided in the Source Data files for Figures 4-6 and Figure 8. These datasets are publicly available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15535117>.

Author contributions

S.N. conceptualization, methodology, analysis, data curation, writing-original draft; K.N, P.J.C. conceptualization, supervision, project administration, review & editing; D.J.G, B.V, J.L. review & editing.

Conflicts of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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